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**SUBJECTIVE AND PERSONAL DETERMINANTS OF
EMOTIONAL STABILITY OF THE PERSONALITY OF THE FUTURE
PSYCHOLOGIST**

**СУБ'ЄКТНО-ОСОБИСТІСНІ ДЕТЕРМІНАНТИ ЕМОЦІЙНОЇ
СТІЙКОСТІ ОСОБИСТОСТІ МАЙБУТНЬОГО ПСИХОЛОГА**

The article discusses the main factors and factors of the development of emotional stability of the future psychologist. The features of the interrelationship of motivational, cognitive, connotative, reflective-value and regulatory-volitional components in the process of developing the emotional stability of the future psychologist in the conditions of challenges and changes are analyzed.

Keywords: *emotional stability, psychological stability, motivation, professional development*

One of the urgent problems of modern psychology is the disclosure of a person's potential in managing his activities. In our opinion, one of the most important problems of health psychology is the identification of so-called «healthy» personality traits (sanogenic potential of the individual) in the process of professional formation, since during the period of the most progressive development of social and professional competencies, the process of developing professional stability can be optimized. One of the most important issues of modern psychological science is the formation and development of the subject's professional and psychological readiness for work, for the creative performance of specific life tasks.

Stability is the most important characteristic of the efficiency, reliability and stability of the professional training of future psychologists, whose activities are extremely important in the conditions of martial law and the transformation of social processes. In psychological science, the concept of «resilience» has several interpretations and terminological combinations: «resilience of personality», «resilience of behavior», «resilience of (professional) activity», «resistance to loads», «emotional resistance», «will resistance», «mental stability», «emotional and volitional stability», «moral stability», «psychological stability», etc. A constituent part of the mental stability of an individual is professional stability, which has a deep tradition of study in domestic and foreign psychology, according to which the modern approach to the study of professional stability is based on understanding it as a quality of the individual and as a mental state that ensures adequate (expedient) behavior of the subject (Аршавя І.Ф., 2006). This approach makes it possible to reveal the prerequisites of professional stability, which lie in the dynamics of the psyche, the content of emotions, feelings, and experiences, as well as to establish the dependence of it (stability) on needs, motives, and will; preparedness, awareness and readiness of the individual to

perform certain tasks dialectically. A significant part of the research is devoted to the consideration of the role of emotions and emotional experiences in various types of activity, in particular educational (Т. Kyrylenko, L. V. Semichenko, O. Chebykin, etc.). The main features of the formed professional stability of the individual, the researchers include: adequate assessment of available energy resources and the ability to rationally use and mobilize them in professional extreme situations; an optimal motivational complex with a harmonious combination of internal and external motives; the ability to assess possible extreme situations and develop appropriate behavioral strategies; the ability to emotional and volitional self-regulation in stressful and extreme conditions (Пилипенко К.В., 2009). Resilience refers to the ability to withstand difficulties, to maintain faith in situations of frustration and a constant (quite high) level of mood. The emotional stability of a person is manifested in two ways. On the one hand, as a person's ability to maintain his personal positions and resist influence, which is contrary to his personal instructions. On the other hand, as the ability to realize one's personal positions by changing circumstances and regulating one's own behavior (Аршава І.Ф., 2006). Emotional stability of the personality can be considered as a complex quality of personality, synthesis of individual qualities and abilities. Emotional stability is supported by internal (personal) resources and external (interpersonal, social support, working conditions). In foreign psychology, less attention is paid to personal factors of stability, more closely considering only a few main ones related to the functioning of the individual in the social environment. Thus, B. Bernard singles out four main personal factors of stability (Семиченко В.А., 2001):

1. Social competence (which includes sensitivity, sociability, empathy, carefulness, compassion, altruism and the ability to forgive).
2. Ability to solve problems (planning abilities, flexibility, resourcefulness, critical thinking, insightful thinking).
3. Autonomy (which includes positive identity, internal locus of control, initiative, self-efficacy, mastery, adaptive distancing from others, resilience, self-awareness, and a sense of humor).
4. Awareness of the goal and the future (which includes goal orientation, orientation to success, motivation to achieve, educational orientation, constancy, optimism, faith in a bright future, sense of consistency, spirituality, meaning of life, creativity, developed imagination).

In the context of the component of an individual's sanogenic potential that we are investigating, the development works of the Center for the Study of Resilience at the University of Minnesota, which developed a special structure for identifying the resiliency of an individual: faith → the ability to overcome adverse conditions → life strategies → individual achievements → social achievements, are interesting (Osadchyi V., Varina H. & others, 2020). This scheme allows you to plan and implement effective preventive programs in the process of developing the sanogenic potential of the future specialist. As a result

of the theoretical analysis, we managed to identify the structure of the emotional stability of the future psychologist, following components: *motivational, cognitive, connotative, reflective and valuable and regulatory-volitional*.

Factors affecting stability personalities:

1) psychological competence, that is, awareness of one's personal, psychophysiological qualities; knowledge of the symptoms, characteristics and picture of a stressful state; awareness of its consequences;

2) life experience, including the behavior in different situations, ways of responding them, formed relations;

3) personal features, including motivation, level of the personal self-regulation, readiness for active actions, mastery of psychoregulatory technologies of behavior; the ability to build interpersonal relationships.

Thus, the main factors affecting the emotional stability of the individual are physiological, behavioral and subjective, social and psychological factors.

Age psychological features play an important role in the development of emotional stability and individual experience of an individual, which are primarily a socio-psychological factor.

Among the urgent needs of modern students of higher education can be highlighted the following: the need for self-knowledge, self-esteem, self-determination, self-education; the psychological and emotional independence, achieving a certain social status, etc.

The main factor of the sanogenic potential of the personality of the future psychologist is directly satisfaction with the chosen profession, which has significant correlations with the optimal motivational complex (positive relationship $r = + 0.409$) and with the level of emotional instability (negative dependence $r = - 0.585$). In other words, the higher the satisfaction with the chosen profession, the more optimal the motivational complex: the high significancy of internal and external positive motivation and the low significancy of external negative motivation. High emotional instability is associated with a decrease in job satisfaction (Varina H., Osadcha K. & others, 2022).

Emotional instability of the personality itself can cause a decrease in job satisfaction in a number of cases. But on the other hand, low satisfaction caused by other reasons (intrapersonal conflict, professional failures, inability to satisfy basic needs, etc.) can lead to increased emotional instability. The first affects the second, the second affects the first; at the same time, the overall negative effect is constantly maintained at a high level or increases. The negative correlative dependence between the optimality of the motivational complex and the level of emotional instability of the personality of the future professional is confirmed by the research. The more optimal the motivational complex, the more the activity of the psychologist is motivated by the very content of the practical activity, the desire to achieve certain positive results in it, the lower the emotional instability. Conversely, the more the activity of the specialist is determined by motives of avoidance, the desire «not to come a howler» (which begin to prevail over

motives, related to the value of psychological activity itself, as well as external positive motivation), the higher the level of emotional instability.

A special category of resources of emotional stability, which should be paid attention to, are strategies and models of coping behavior. The nature and methods of coping with stressful situations depend on the life position, activity of the individual, on his needs for self-realization of his potentials and abilities.

It is possible to draw a conclusion about the external and internal psychological factors of the emotional stability of the individual. The assessment of the stressful situation, which covers the objective and subjective parameters of the stressful situation, is classified as external; strategies for overcoming stress, or coping behavior; the impact of traumatic events on the personality and the degree of processing of the traumatic experience; social support; professional and personal experience; psychological preparation for activities in extreme conditions.

Emotional stability as an integrative property of the individual involves interaction with all structural characteristics of the psyche, both during and after stressogenic factors. Thus, the determining internal factors of the formation and development of the emotional stability of the personality include the self-concept of the personality, the development of the communicative sphere, the content characteristics of the structural components of the personality's stress resistance. In particular, a high level of emotional stability implies poise, self-confidence, the fight against shyness, a low level of personal anxiety, self-control, self-control; certain characteristics of the motivational sphere (motivation of the social significance of work, professional skills, achievements). The speed of processing information, the mobility of nervous processes, reliability, endurance, accuracy and productivity of activities are considered to be the defining characteristics of primary stress resistance. The leading strategies for dealing with stress that characterize emotional stability are assertive actions, personal activity in interaction, and the search for social support and social contacts.

The mechanism of manifestation of emotional stability can be described using a two-level structure: the primary level of stress resistance, which is based on a biological component: emotional tone, endurance, accuracy, functional mobility, reliability, the main characteristics and features of the main nervous processes, the level of activation, a complex of constitutional and genetic, physiological, endocrine and other systems that ensure its adequate and stable functioning in stressful conditions and personal characteristics that are the result of social influence, experience, training. Although the primary level is basic in the formation of emotional stability, the decisive importance is given to personal, social, behavioral components and training.

So, we determined that the concept of «emotional stability» has an integral, dynamic character based on the balance between all spheres of human life between the needs of a person and society. The main characteristics of an emotionally stable person are his autonomy, creativity, sense of humor, tolerance,

positive thinking, ability to take risks, hedonistic attitude to life and others. Having analyzed the concept of stress resistance, we specialized the determinants of emotional stability, the main ones of which are: focus, acquired experience, mental processes, features of character and temperament. The main functions of emotional stability were determined: focus on overcoming obstacles; actualization of activities in extreme conditions; stabilization of internal mechanisms of emotional and volitional self-regulation. Emotional stability is influenced by coping strategies and psychological resources, thus, it is individual psychological conditions that play an important role in the formation of emotional stability.